

Recommended citation: Karvinen, M., Grindsted, T. S., Keränen, A., Hermansen, J. E., Selbekk, L. K., Sohlo, S., & Sorvari, J. (2017). Sustainability Literacy and Engineering Experiences From a Literacy Test as a Teaching and Assessment Tool in Nordic Universities. In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 49-62). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14697989.

Sustainability literacy and engineering
Experiences from a literacy test as a teaching and assessment tool in Nordic universities

M Karvinen¹

Doctoral candidate
Aalto University, Department of Built Environment
Espoo, Finland
E-mail: meeri.karvinen@aalto.fi

TS Grindsted

Lecturer, Geography and Planning
Roskilde University, Department of People and Technology
Roskilde, Denmark
E-mail: tskoug@ruc.dk

A Keränen

Lecturer
University of Oulu, Martti Ahtisaari Institute
Oulu, Finland
E-mail: anne.keranen@oulu.fi

JE Hermansen

Associate professor
NTNU, Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management
Trondheim, Norway
E-mail: john.hermansen@ntnu.no

LK Selbekk

Research assistant
NTNU, Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management
Trondheim, Norway
E-mail: larskrse@gmail.com

S Sohlo

Deputy Director
University of Oulu, Martti Ahtisaari Institute
Oulu, Finland
E-mail: sauli.sohlo@oulu.fi

¹ Corresponding Author
M Karvinen
meeri.karvinen@aalto.fi

J Sorvari

Associate professor

Aalto University, Department of Built Environment

Espoo, Finland

E-mail: jaana.sorvari@aalto.fi

ABSTRACT

The role of engineering education is essential in global sustainability transformation, considering the impact technology has on the environment and societies. Many suggestions have been made on what competences universities should teach to educate game changers and how to improve sustainability literacy. Despite the growing number of studies in the field, research is scarce on how to assess what the students know about global sustainability challenges and how to embed sustainability literacy into curricula. This paper presents the first experiences on using a sustainability literacy test (the Sulitest) as a teaching tool. The test was developed in 2012, and it includes global and national questions on multifaceted sustainability challenges. Our results are based on national questions created for the Nordic countries and on the test results we got from 700 students in Finland, Sweden and Norway. The Sulitest seems to be useful as a teaching tool, but the national questions ought to be re-evaluated to achieve balance between different aspects of sustainability. The test has weaknesses regarding its use as a curricula development tool, but it can facilitate teachers in engineering education in drawing a comprehensive picture on the problems the future engineers are required to solve.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Curriculum Development, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Sustainability Learning, Literacy Test, Nordic universities

INTRODUCTION

Engineering education needs to adapt to the global sustainability transformation, which has been widely acknowledged [1]. Engineering associations in the west point to competences for solving 21st century challenges, and a number of scholars find engineering curricula in the midst of a paradigm change from “how to integrate sustainability into our discipline” to “how our discipline can contribute to sustainability” [2, 3]. Such scholars emphasise that engineers need holistic understanding on the environmental, societal and economic impacts of their profession, and advocate for generic and interdisciplinary skills. Moreover, engineering education should focus also on the values, behaviour and problem solving skills in order to solve wicked problems, in addition to the technical expertise and specific knowledge they acquire from their studies.

Many teachers worldwide have made efforts to tackle the challenge of combining sustainability transformation and engineering education. Contributions vary from individual methods, including online learning [4], games [5] and concept maps [6] to wider measures such as a dedicated program for sustainability engineering combining different engineering fields [7], multiple course-specific sustainability components integrated in chemical engineering curricula courses [8] and integrating sustainability into learning

outcomes of courses or programs [9]. By way of illustration Segalas et al. [9] study three European technical universities' bachelor programs, and find none of the sustainability competences under investigation contained a learning outcome "world current situation", despite of the otherwise sustainability-oriented learning outcomes.

In fact, in the global research concerning sustainability in higher education, the question of key sustainability competences has raised debate over what and how, we should teach in order to empower the students to contribute to sustainability transition [see for example 10, 11]. Some of the most commonly agreed competences are systems thinking, integrative and holistic thinking, strategic and collaborative competences [12], whereas some of the most used teaching methods across disciplines include problem-based learning, case studies, group discussions and critical writing tasks [13].

However, knowledge on current global sustainability challenges, "the world current situation", is a fundamental precondition for learning on how to promote sustainability transition. According to UNESCO [14], education for sustainable development (ESD) should include several issues, including climate change, biodiversity, poverty and disaster reduction, sustainable consumptions and market adaptation. Moreover, engineering innovates solutions to sustainability challenges in one scale, but may produce sustainability challenges in another. Therefore, there is a need to define what should be included in this "basic knowledge set" of world's current situation.

One opening was made in 2012 in the form of an international, internet-based test containing different global challenges, and covering all the pillars of sustainability. This Sustainability Literacy Test (Sulitest) was created as the response to the goals set in the United Nation's (UN) Rio+20 world sustainability summit, and it's also closely aligned to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the UN Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development. Sulitest development was guided by over 300 contributors and its panel of senior and regional advisors, including the UN, the UN Development Program (UNDP), the Globally Responsible Leadership Initiative (GRLI), the UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the International Association of Universities.

The test aims to facilitate higher education teachers to assess their students' knowledge and skills on sustainability and works as a means for testing participants' sustainability awareness. The Sulitest has already been adopted to hundreds of universities all over the world, and over 40000 students have taken the test by the end of 2016. However, scientific discussion is yet to be opened on its benefits and disadvantages as a teaching and assessment tool in higher education. In fact, research in general is very scarce concerning the use of tests as teaching or assessing tools in sustainability education.

This paper discusses the first experiences gained from the Sulitest in a Nordic project, which aimed to find new ways to evaluate student's sustainability literacy across disciplines. The paper examines features of the Sulitest and Nordic university students' sustainability literacy, and discusses the test as a tool for integrating sustainability into engineering education. Finally, the paper reflects on how making engineering and interdisciplinary study can contribute to sustainability, to paraphrase Mulder [3]. The results will benefit teachers in higher education interested in promoting sustainability literacy, regardless of discipline, to familiarize themselves with different aspects of the Sulitest.

1 NORDIC SULITEST PROJECT

1.1. Sustainability in Nordic higher education

The Nordic countries are renowned for their ambitious strategies for sustainable development, and they target at leading the way in ESD [15, 16]. For example, at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), interdisciplinary environmental oriented courses with different approaches and perspectives have been mandatory for the engineering students for more than 25 years and according to a recent overview from the NTNU Sustainability Programme, more than a 100 courses are connected to sustainability concepts [17]. However, recent research has on the other hand suggested that Nordic universities follow a global trend [18, 19] in emphasizing campus operations over sustainability education [20], and that sustainability is inefficiently integrated in the learning outcomes of Nordic universities' courses and programs [21]. Moreover, Boman and Andersson [22] found that only 1/3 of the courses in the University of Gothenburg, Sweden, include sustainability contents.

The factors affecting sustainability integration in higher education are multifaceted. In the research done in the Nordic countries, mainly focused on Swedish case examples, the role of good leadership, clear strategy, environmental management systems and collaboration have been highlighted to promote institutional sustainability [23-26]. However, major global challenges for teachers to integrate sustainability in their teaching seem to be overcrowded curricula, lack of resources or insufficient competences in sustainability [27-29]. Therefore, evaluation tools, such as the Sulitest, with which teachers could get an understanding of the students' sustainability competences, while students acquire sustainability knowledge and obtain generic competences, would be useful.

1.2. Description of the project

The Sulitest is designed to include a global set of questions (module) and a regional/local module. All researchers and teachers are free to suggest questions for the global question pool, after which they are validated by a Sulitest board and added to the test platform. However, in the case of the local questions, it is up to each country or region if the questions will be created or not. The Nordic universities took the challenge in 2015-2016 and created national modules for Finland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark and the Faroe Islands, utilizing the experiences acquired from the first pilot test in Finland during 2014-2015. Also additional 5 questions on Nordic-level sustainability challenges were included in each national module. The final number of questions in the new modules varied between 25 and 31, depending on the country.

The project included also the piloting of the new questions with each partnering universities' students. Four Nordic universities from Norway, Sweden and Finland piloted the Sulitest with their national modules during spring 2017. This paper is based on the results from those pilots. The piloting institutions chose themselves the matrix design of using the Sulitest: as an assessment tool for exploring sustainability literacy, as a teaching tool offering the students the opportunity to study the Sulitest questions with the references they include, or as a tool to introduce the students to the subject. Moreover, all the institutions were instructed to ask the students to fill in an optional background

survey following the 50 Sulitest questions, which includes questions on age, gender, discipline and interest toward sustainability.

1.3 Description of the Sulitest architecture

One important feature of the test is the architecture of the questions: the questions should be designed so that there are equal amount of questions belonging to each Sulitest-theme. Preferably, the distribution should be even also in the 24 subjects classified under the 7 themes (see Table 1 for the themes and subjects). Moreover, to facilitate research purposes, the questions must be tagged with at least one sub-subject out of 42, which tells even more precisely what sustainability challenge is discussed in that question.

Table 1. The architecture of the Sulitest: themes and subjects.

Themes	Subjects
1. Sustainable humanity and ecosystems on planet Earth	1. Ecosystems: Biosphere, global and local ecosystems, interdependent and diverse community of life, life supporting cycles, system closed (materials) / open (energy), etc. 2. Humanity: Individual human needs, diversity, social fabric, cultures, local and global world, etc 3. Sustainability: Definition of Sustainability / Sustainable development 4. Ecological perspective : where are we at, and why sustainability is both an urgency and an opportunity 5. Social perspective : where are we at (demography, (in)equalities, gender equality, education, ...), and sustainability being an urgency and an opportunity
2. Global and local human-constructed systems to answer people's needs	6. Local and global social structures and governance: paradigms; positive results negative impacts; laws; how organisations work; land use; gender equality; etc. 7. Within local and global social structures and governance, zooms on : Education, and Culture 8. Local and global economic systems: paradigms; positive results negative impacts; production, distribution, consumption of goods and services; life cycles; value chains; finances; etc. 9. Within local and global economic system, zooms on : Water, Energy, and Food
3. Transitions towards sustainability	10. How to start, reinforce, accelerate systems change 11. Initiatives towards sustainability ... more from institution / int'l level (like UN MDGs, Global Compact, GIEC, GRI, ISO 26000, ESD, etc.) 12. Concepts, tools, frameworks ... more from individual NGOs or smaller networks (like Cradle to Cradle, Natural Capitalism, The Natural Step, Ecological Footprint, etc.) 13. Examples and ideas we can learn from: case studies of successes or failures ; technological, strategic, or social innovations
4. We each have roles to play to create and maintain individual and systemic changes	14. How does one become aware of his own roles and impacts ... whoever "one "is (individual, organisation, south, north, etc.) 15. How does one efficiently act to create both individual and system change ... whoever "one "is (individual, organisation, south, north, etc.)
5. Personal Skills	16. Ability to reflect/self-evaluate alone and in a group; Ability to constantly renew energy; Ability to continuously to learn/develop; Creativity; Critical thinking 17. Capacity for empathy, compassion, solidarity; Futures-oriented and strategic thinking 18. Dealing with complexity and uncertainty; Practical problem-solving / management / planning skills
6. Working with others	19. Networking; Communication skills; building effective coalitions for systemic change 20. Catalysing / managing change; Inspire a shared vision; Enable/Motivating others to act/participate 21. Teamwork; Work in multi-cultural and interdisciplinary (diverse) settings; Participatory skills, decision-making; Conflict resolution skills/consensus building; Focus on process, dialogue, listening;
7. Think and act systemically	22. Ability to put in practice systems thinking concepts; identify and use leverage points 23. Ability to zoom in and out in time and details, and to keep the desired future and global perspective in mind 24. Ability to understand formal and informal structures, power dynamics, and interactions

This paper presents the first results of sustainability literacy levels of Nordic higher education students, and preliminary descriptions on the factors affecting the test results. Moreover, the aim is to initiate discussion on the Sulitest as a tool for sustainability education. For the tool is rather new, it's essential to explore the quality of the created

national questions, and what causes may lie behind the questions revealing to be among the easiest or the most demanding ones.

The detailed research questions are:

1. What are the average scores of Finnish, Swedish and Norwegian students?
2. Which factors affect the scores of the Nordic students?
3. How equally the national questions are distributed to the different Sulitest themes?
4. Do the different modules of the Sulitest include questions that are on average very easy or very demanding (over 70% respond correctly / incorrectly)?
5. If there are clear differences in the degree of difficulty of certain questions, are there any common factors in the questions that may explain the trend?

2 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND METHODS

The motivation for this study was to explore the usability of the Sustainability Literacy Test (Sulitest) as a teaching and curricula-development tool. We succeeded in having test results from 3 technical and 2 other universities in Norway, Sweden and Finland, the amount of responses being finally 700 in total. The students represented multiple fields, including business, law, water and environmental engineering, sustainability, environmental sciences, environmental management and corporate governance.

The main purpose of the Nordic project's pilots was to gain experiences on how the test could be used in teaching, and to explore if there were too trivial or too demanding questions. Moreover, the project signalled the importance of sustainability issues to students, and that the topic is of great concern to higher education institutions. The most demanding and easiest questions were defined to be those, which <70% or >70% answered correctly, respectively, and were analysed with qualitative content analyses to find out the possible factors explaining the difficulty/easiness. The content analyses was conducted using open coding, based on which classifications for easy and difficult questions were created. The factors affecting the students' sustainability literacy were analysed quantitatively.

As the data was not collected with an empirical research setting, the backgrounds and amounts of students varied substantially between the piloting institutions. Therefore, the approach of this study is explorative, and the results on the students' literacy only suggestive. Moreover, the limited amount of background survey data allowed quantitative analyses for only some of the surveyed factors (only 220 students answered the survey).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Which factors affect Sulitest scores?

The total scores of the students from Finland and Norway were a bit above international reference scores (51% for international module). In all the countries, the international module seemed to be easier for the students compared to the national module. The total results for Sweden were significantly lower compared with both Finland ($p < 0,001$, $F = 19,193$, one-way Anova) and Norway ($p < 0,21$, $F = 19,193$). All the average scores are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The averages of the Sulitest scores from Finland, Sweden and Norway. In counting the national module scores, the results from the students who indicated in the Sulitest background survey being of other nationality than Finnish, Swedish or Norwegian, were excluded.

Sulitest Module (n of questions responded)	Countries							
	Finland		Sweden		Norway		All countries	
	N respondents	% correct						
International (30)	199	57%	453	50%	48	60%	700	53%
National (20)	157	50%	440	44%	40	46%	637	47%
All questions (50)	199	53%	453	45%	48	52%	700	48%

The vast majority of all the respondents represented Master’s degree students, except for Sweden, where 44% of the 106 students who responded the background survey, were bachelor students. However, there was no statistically significant differences between the scores of bachelor and master students, but instead, age seemed to have a positive correlation with the total test score (Fig. 1, $r=0,22$, $p<0,001$). Gender instead had no effect on the total scores.

The students responding the Sulitest represented mostly business, law and engineering fields, with only a few students representing other fields, such as arts, humanities and communications. However, since 82% of the 220 students who indicated their discipline in the background survey, represented business and law, the effect of discipline on the scores was not explored.

Figure 1. There was a positive correlation between age and total scores of the Sulitest ($r=0,22$, $p<0,001$), $N = 256$.

The nationality of the students seemed to have a minor, yet not significant, effect on the scores: the Nordic nationalities scored better in the national modules compared to the nationalities coming from outside of Nordic countries (international students), whereas the international students scored on average slightly better in the international module (Table 3). Moreover, minor difference was observed between different Nordic nationalities in answering two joint Nordic questions: The Finnish respondents scored better (49%) in a question concerning the eutrophication of the Baltic Sea compared to the Swedish (29%) and Norwegian (25%), whereas the Swedish had better level of knowledge (88%) on the Nordic ecolabel Swan's contents than the Finnish students (40%) (the Norwegians did not answer the Swan-question).

Table 3. The average results of international students compared to Nordic nationalities. The results include only the students who responded the background survey.

Sulitest module	Nordic students		International	
	N	% correct	N	% correct
International	200	55%	58	59%
Finnish	68	50%	37	44%
Swedish	113	45%	13	43%
Norwegian	19	53%	8	36%
All questions	200	50%	58	52%

However, when exploring the effects of sustainability involvement or interest, which were asked in the background survey, there was a statistically significant difference between those who indicated they keep up with the news about sustainability often (n=74, score=57%) compared to those keeping up about the news only rarely (n=128, score=48%), (F=19,863, p<0,001, one-way Anova).

3.2 Quality of the questions

The quality of the national questions varied. The Norwegian module included several questions that revealed to be very challenging, as well as the Swedish module, while the Finnish questions all seemed to be moderate in their level of difficulty (Fig. 3). In all the national modules, theme number 4 was underrepresented compared to the number of questions in other themes, and in Finnish and Swedish modules themes 1 and 2 were somewhat overrepresented (Table 4).

Table 4. The distribution of questions used in the pilots according to Sulitest themes.

Theme	Module				
	International	Finnish	Swedish	Norwegian	All
1. Sustainable humanity and ecosystems on planet Earth	9	4	9	8	30
2. Global and local human-constructed systems to answer people's needs	10	11	11	5	37
3. Transitions towards sustainability	9	8	8	6	31
4. We each have roles to play to create and maintain individual and systemic changes	2	2	2	2	8
5. Personal Skills			1	3	3
6. Working with others				3	3
7. Think and act systemically				3	4
All themes	30	25	31	30	116

Figure 3. The difference in questions' difficulty in each module: In the Norwegian module, there are more difficult questions compared to the other modules.

Of all the 116 questions used in the pilot sessions, 25 revealed to be on average relatively difficult (<30% of respondents correct), and 9 relatively easy (>70% respondents correct). No explicit factors were found to explain why those particular questions were easy or difficult: they represented multiple subjects and themes. However, questions including statistics seemed to be challenging, specifically when the answering options were close to each other. The most difficult questions also required in many cases detailed knowledge on certain field, and the answering options were well designed making it hard to guess the expected answer. On the contrary, some of the easiest questions were designed in a way, which revealed the correct answer in the formulation of the question. In a few cases the correct answers were also quite evident, as the incorrect answering options were somewhat irrelevant considering the question formulation. (Table 5.).

Table 5. Factors affecting the difficulty of questions.

	Specific information on a field or actors	Statistics	Terminology	Correct answer can be guessed	General knowledge
Difficult questions	18	5	2		
Easy questions	1		1	4	3

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Having examined a cohort of 700 responses from students in Norway, Finland and Sweden, this section discusses the main findings. The results are examined against Mulder [3] on how engineering education may contribute to sustainability and how the results indicate interdisciplinary challenges.

Students indicating they follow the media on sustainability subjects seemed to score relatively high in the Sulitest. In addition, the easiest questions in the pilots revealed to include several subjects that are widely discussed in the Nordic public media, such as the effects of Chernobyl radiation, high global costs of climate change or the amount of electric cars in Norway. These results, added with the positive correlation of age and scores, suggest that sustainability literacy discussed in the Sulitest questions measures respondents' level of awareness, all-round education and personal interest, rather than the level a university has been teaching sustainability subjects. Thus, the Sulitest can be recommended only with caution as a tool to assess sustainability contents of curricula.

In addition, the questions used in the test vary from session to session due to the design of the Sulitest online platform: the system randomly selects a set of questions from a larger pool to a single test session. However, we found also the quality of the questions, as well as the representativeness of different Sulitest themes, varying substantially. The uneven distribution of questions concerning different themes may result in biases in students' scores: students having more experience from their studies concerning themes 1-2 might score higher than their peers studying a field that has emphasis on themes 3 or 4 (see Table 1 for the themes). This might make comparisons between different institutions or disciplines unreliable. We therefore suggest the national modules to be developed to a more balanced direction. Moreover, our findings suggest that the strength the Sulitest resides in its ability to evaluate progress from course to course, or within a course, rather than in comparing the scores between students, institutions or countries.

Thus, due to the imbalance of questions representing different themes, we recommend the test to be used by teachers as an introduction to sustainability, or as a teaching tool making good use of the references each question of the Sulitest includes. Segalas et al. [9], for example, called for a common definition on sustainability competences for engineering curricula to facilitate sustainability integration. Sulitest could, if properly developed, offer a framework for teaching world's current situation, reasons behind unsustainability, technological development and ability to act and solve problems. However, one needs to acknowledge that knowledge is not the only factor affecting the environmental performance of a person, but several factors contribute to it, such as country and culture, informal education, and personal motivation and attitudes [30]. To which degree students actually acquire sustainability knowledge and obtain generic competences in higher education was beyond the scope of this study, and invitations to study engineering pedagogy and the use of tests is most welcome.

For future development, we suggest re-evaluation of all the national modules to have appropriate and equal quality and balance between the themes. In addition, we recommend detailed analyses to be made on the students' test results before drawing conclusions on their literacy or making decisions on the curricula according to the test results. Moreover, an empirical study would be needed to investigate more thoroughly the factors having an effect on students' sustainability literacy, such as nationality, age or discipline. The fact that different Nordic nationalities gained varying results from a few questions on Nordic-level sustainability, is also interesting and raises a question if sustainability challenges or actions often considered Nordic, are after all more relevant to specific countries than to the whole region, and the subject could offer possibilities for

future research with the Sulitest. Finally, it would be interesting to investigate teachers' motivation to use the test, for it contains many aspects beneficial for higher education.

To conclude, we consider the potential of the Sulitest substantial in teaching global sustainability challenges in universities. According to a short questionnaire by one piloting institution, the test revealed to be eye-opening for many students, presenting the considerable diversity of different fields, challenges, solutions, definitions, management practices and agreements relating to sustainability, added with references to the question sources. Therefore, despite its weaknesses as an assessment or curricula development tool, it can facilitate the teachers also in engineering education substantially in drawing a comprehensive picture on the problems the future engineers are required to solve, and on the interdisciplinary and interconnected nature of future working life.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We want to express our warmest gratitude to all partners in the Nordic project, and all the experts involved in creating the national modules. We additionally want to thank the Sulitest organization for the smooth collaboration and assistance in creating the national modules. This study wouldn't have been possible without the kind permission from the piloting universities to use the students' Sulitest results for analyses. The Nordic Sulitest project was funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Crawley E, Malmqvist J, Ostlund S and Brodeur D (2007), Rethinking engineering education, *The CDIO Approach*, 302, pp. 60-62.
- [2] Corcoran PB and Wals AEJ (2004), Higher education and the challenge of sustainability, problematics, promise, and practice. Springer, Germany.
- [3] Mulder KF (2017), Strategic competences for concrete action towards sustainability: An oxymoron? Engineering education for a sustainable future, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 68, pp. 1106-1111.
- [4] Sivapalan S, Clifford MJ, and Speight S (2017), Engineering education for sustainable development: using online learning to support the new paradigms. *Australasian Journal of Engineering Education*, 1-13.
- [5] Pargman D, Hedin B, and Eriksson E (2016), Patterns of Engagement: Using a board game as a tool to address sustainability in engineering educations. In EESD2016—Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Engineering Education for Sustainable Development, Bruges, 4-7 September 2016 – Building a circular economy together, pp. 302-310, Instituut vóór Duurzame Ontwikkeling vzw.
- [6] Barrella EM, and Watson MK (2016), Comparing the outcomes of horizontal and vertical integration of sustainability content into engineering curricula using concept maps. In New developments in engineering education for sustainable development, pp 1-13, Springer International Publishing.

- [7] Brennan RA, and Riley DR (2016), A new program in sustainable engineering: a platform for integrating research and service into the classroom through global engagement. In *New Developments in Engineering Education for Sustainable Development*, pp. 15-21, Springer International Publishing.
- [8] Allen DT, Shonnard DR, Huang Y, and Schuster D (2016), Green Engineering Education in Chemical Engineering Curricula: A Quarter Century of Progress and Prospects for Future Transformations, pp. 5850-5854.
- [9] Segalàs J, Ferrer-Balas D, Svanström M, Lundqvist U, and Mulder KF (2009), What has to be learnt for sustainability? A comparison of bachelor engineering education competences at three European universities, *Sustainability Science*, 4(1), 17.
- [10] Sterling S (Ed.) (2010), *Sustainability education: Perspectives and practice across higher education*, Taylor & Francis.
- [11] Wood BE, Cornforth S, Beals F, Taylor M and Tallon R (2016), Sustainability champions? Academic identities and sustainability curricula in higher education, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 17(3), pp. 342-360.
- [12] Wiek A, Withycombe L, and Redman CL (2011), Key competencies in sustainability: a reference framework for academic program development, *Sustainability science*, 6(2), pp. 203-218.
- [13] Cotton D, and Winter J (2010), It's not just bits of paper and light bulbs. A review of sustainability pedagogies and their potential for use in higher education, In *Sustainability education: Perspectives and practice across higher education*, pp. 39-54.
- [14] UNESCO 2015, Education for Sustainable Development, <http://en.unesco.org/themes/education-sustainable-development>
- [15] Nordic Council of Ministers (2009), *Sustainable Development – New Bearings for the Nordic Countries*, Scanprint A/S, Copenhagen.
- [16] Nordic Council of Ministers (2011), *Knowledge for Green Growth and Welfare: The Council of Ministers for Education and Research's MR-U Strategy for Education and Research 2011–2013*, Arco Grafisk A/S, Skive.
- [17] Hermansen JE (2010), Samfunn, miljø og bedrift – fragmenter fra miljøundervisning i 40 år ved NTH/NTNU og ORAL/IØT. I Sletten, P.G. (red): *Glimt av hundre års virksomhet*. Institutt for industriell økonomi og teknologiledelse, NTNU, pp 167-185.

- [18] Wals AEJ (2014), Sustainability in higher education in the context of the UN DESD: a review of learning and institutionalization processes, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 62, pp. 8-15.
- [19] Ramos TB, Caeiro S, van Hoof B, Lozano R, Huisingh D and Ceulemans K (2015), Experiences from the implementation of sustainable development in higher education institutions: Environmental Management for Sustainable Universities, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 106, pp. 3-10.
- [20] Karvinen M, Lundgren U, Mälkki H, and Sorvari J (2017), The Implementation of Sustainable Development in the Nordic Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). In *Handbook of Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development in Higher Education* pp. 169-187, Springer International Publishing.
- [21] Karvinen M, Mälkki H, and Sorvari J (2016), How sustainable Nordic higher education actually is? Exploring the role of sustainable development in teaching at Nordic Higher Education Institutions, 44th European Society for Engineering Education SEFI Conference, Tampere: Engineering Education on Top of the World: Industry University Cooperation.
- [22] Boman UP and Andersson (2013), Eco-labelling of courses and programs at University of Gothenburg, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 48, pp. 48–53.
- [23] Sammalisto K (2007), Environmental Management Systems – a Way towards Sustainable Development in Universities, Doctoral dissertation: The International Institute for Industrial Environmental Economics (IIIEE), Lund University, Sweden.
- [24] Holm T, Sammalisto K, Vuorisalo T and Grindsted TS (2012), A model for enhancing education for sustainable development with management systems: experiences from the Nordic countries. Leal Filho W. (Ed.), *Sustainable Development at Universities: New Horizons*. Peter Lang Scientific Publishers, Frankfurt am Main, pp. 261–272.
- [25] Holmberg J, Lundqvist U, Svanström M and Arehag M (2012), The university and transformation towards sustainability: The strategy used at Chalmers University of Technology, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 13(3), pp. 219–231.
- [26] Finnveden G, Egan ED, Sandberg T, and Strömberg E (2017), A Holistic Approach for Integration of Sustainable Development in Education, Research, Collaboration and Operations, In *Handbook of Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development in Higher Education*, pp. 287-303, Springer International Publishing.
- [27] Jones P, Trier CJ and Richards JP (2008), Embedding education for sustainable development in higher education: A case study examining common challenges and

opportunities for undergraduate programmes, *International Journal of Educational Research*, 47(6), pp. 341–350.

- [28] Læssøe J, Schnack K, Breiting S and Rolls S (2009), Climate Change and Sustainable Development. The Response from Education: a Cross-national Report from International Alliance of Leading Education Institutes Danmarks Pædagogiske Universitetsskole, Aarhus Universitet, Copenhagen.
- [29] Leal Filho W (2011), About the role of universities and their contribution to sustainable development, *Higher Education Policy*, 24, pp. 427–438.
- [30] Vicente-Molina MA, Fernández-Sáinz A, and Izagirre-Olaizola J (2013), Environmental knowledge and other variables affecting pro-environmental behaviour: comparison of university students from emerging and advanced countries, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 61, pp. 130-138.